

Attitude toward public service delivery and competency of barangay health workers in the First District of Capiz, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) play a vital role in strengthening primary healthcare systems, particularly in rural and underserved communities in the Philippines. However, they often operate under constrained conditions, including meager financial allowances and limited formal training in health-related fields. Existing studies have largely emphasized technical competencies and programmatic interventions, with insufficient attention to the motivational and attitudinal factors that sustain performance under such constraints. Moreover, attitudes and competencies are frequently examined as separate constructs, resulting in fragmented evidence on workforce effectiveness. In the context of the Philippines' decentralized health system and the implementation of Universal Health Care, a critical gap remains in understanding how public service attitudes may compensate for structural limitations and influence competency among frontline health workers. This study examined the relationship between attitudes toward public service delivery and the competency of BHWs in the First District of Capiz, Philippines. Using a descriptive–correlational design, data were collected from 1,102 randomly selected BHWs across five municipalities. Standardized instruments measured attitudes and competencies across key domains, including organizing and interpersonal skills, primary healthcare services, maternal health, and child health. Results showed very satisfactory levels of public service attitude ($M = 3.68$) and high competency ($M = 3.62$). Significant differences in both attitudes and competency were observed when grouped according to age, educational attainment, employment status, length of service, BHW category, and municipality, while no differences were found in terms of sex and civil status. A strong positive and statistically significant relationship was identified between attitudes and competency ($r = 0.758$, $p < .01$), indicating that more positive service-oriented attitudes are associated with higher levels of competency. The findings underscore the role of intrinsic motivation in sustaining performance despite resource constraints, highlighting the need for policies that integrate capacity-building with recognition and support systems.

Keywords: Barangay health workers, competency assessment, attitudes toward public service, capacity-building, primary health care delivery.

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INTRODUCTION

Health is a fundamental pillar of community development, influencing productivity, social stability, and quality of life (Hartigan-Go et al., 2023). In the Philippines, persistent disparities in healthcare access—particularly in rural and underserved areas—continue to challenge health system effectiveness (Ramos, 2025). The Universal Health Care Act was enacted to address these inequities through a strengthened primary healthcare (PHC) system, emphasizing accessible and community-based service delivery (Naria-Maritana et al., 2020).

Within this framework, Barangay Health Workers (BHWs), recognized under Republic Act 7883, serve as essential frontline providers linking households to the formal health system. However, their performance is shaped by structural constraints, including limited training opportunities, inconsistent supervision, and modest financial incentives in the form of honoraria and allowances rather than formal salaries, as reflected in House Bill No. 3656. These conditions raise critical questions about how BHWs sustain effective service delivery in resource-constrained settings.

The effectiveness of BHWs can be understood through both competency and attitudinal dimensions. Competence refers to the knowledge and skills necessary for healthcare delivery, while attitudes toward public service reflect commitment, altruism, and willingness to serve. These dimensions are inherently interconnected, particularly among community-based workers with diverse educational backgrounds. This perspective is supported by Public Service Motivation, which emphasizes the role of intrinsic values in driving performance (Holt, 2018).

Despite this, existing literature has largely examined competency and attitudes as separate constructs, with limited empirical evidence on their interaction, particularly in the Philippine context. This fragmentation constrains a comprehensive understanding of how motivational factors may compensate for structural limitations, such as low financial incentives and limited formal training, in sustaining frontline health service delivery.

In the First District of Capiz, variations in healthcare access across municipalities further highlight the need to strengthen BHW performance. This study therefore investigates the relationship between attitudes toward public service delivery and the competence of BHWs. By integrating motivational and capability-based perspectives, the study aims to contribute to the literature and inform policies that enhance training, supervision, and support mechanisms for community-based healthcare under the Universal Health Care framework.

Statement of the problem

This study aimed to examine the attitudes toward public service delivery and the competency of Barangay Health Workers in the First District of Capiz, Philippines. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What profile can be drawn from the respondents in terms of municipality, age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, outside employment, length of service, and BHW category?
2. What is the level of attitudes toward public service delivery among Barangay Health Workers?
3. What is the level of competency of Barangay Health Workers as a whole and in terms of organizing orientation and building interpersonal relationships, delivering primary healthcare services, providing healthcare services related to safe motherhood and women's health, and delivering healthcare services concerning child health?

4. Is there a significant difference in the level of attitudes toward public service delivery when respondents are grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of competency when respondents are grouped according to their profile?
6. Is there a significant relationship between attitudes toward public service delivery and the competency of Barangay Health Workers?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive–correlational research design to examine the attitudes toward public service delivery and the competency of Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) in the First District of Capiz, Philippines. The design enabled the systematic description of respondents’ profiles, attitudes, and competencies, as well as the analysis of relationships and differences across selected variables without manipulating the research setting, ensuring ecological validity (Creswell, 1994; Johnson & Christensen, 2007). The study was conducted in five municipalities—Pontevedra, Panay, Panitan, Maayon, and President Roxas—covering predominantly rural and semi-urban communities where BHWs serve as frontline healthcare providers. A total of 1,102 respondents were randomly selected. Ethical standards for human subject research were observed. Informed consent was obtained, and participants’ confidentiality, privacy, and autonomy were ensured.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of three parts: respondent profile, attitudes toward public service delivery (adapted from Taburnal, 2017), and competency across key healthcare domains (adapted from Gonzales et al., 2024). A four-point Likert scale was used to measure both attitudes and competencies. Data gathering was carried out through coordination with local government units and health offices, with trained enumerators administering the survey after securing informed consent. Ethical standards, including confidentiality and voluntary participation, were strictly observed.

For analysis, descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, while non-parametric tests (Mann–Whitney U and Kruskal–Wallis) were applied due to non-normal distribution. Spearman’s rho was used to determine the relationship between attitudes and competency, with all tests set at a 0.05 level of significance.

This study was made possible through internal funding support from Capiz State University, which facilitated data collection, field coordination, and overall implementation of the research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Results and Discussion section is grounded in data collected from Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) across five municipalities in the First District of Capiz, namely Pontevedra (30.7%), Panay (20.2%), Maayon (20.1%), Panitan (15.3%), and President Roxas (13.6%), ensuring comprehensive district representation. The respondents were predominantly within the 46–55 age group (34.3%), followed by 36–45 years (28.0%) and 56–65 years (20.7%), with smaller proportions from other age groups. The workforce was overwhelmingly female (99.4%), and the majority were married (90.5%). Educational attainment revealed that 32.7% had reached college level and 27.9% were high school graduates, while 68.3% were unemployed. In terms of experience, 48.2% had 10 years or less of service, 36.8% had 11–20 years, and the rest had longer tenures. Regarding classification, 61.8% were registered BHWs, 26.7% were registered and certified, and 11.5% were volunteers. Using a descriptive correlational research design, data were gathered through structured survey instruments and

analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential techniques, including mean, standard deviation, and Pearson *r*. The discussion that follows is strictly anchored on these data and interprets the findings in direct relation to the study's objectives on attitudes toward public service delivery and competency.

The level of attitude toward public service delivery among BHWs was found to be very satisfactory, with an overall mean of $M = 3.6759$ and $SD = .37262$. All indicators reflected consistently high ratings, with willingness to conduct voluntary service receiving the highest mean of $M = 3.7160$ and $SD = .51684$, followed by readiness to be of service with a smile at $M = 3.6969$ and $SD = .54479$, and increased morale when community recognizes BHW work also at $M = 3.6969$ and $SD = .53469$. Other closely rated indicators included love for work at $M = 3.6942$ and $SD = .54908$, self fulfillment when providing service at $M = 3.6770$ and $SD = .54830$, encouragement to work harder when improvements in client health are visible at $M = 3.6688$ and $SD = .55743$, willingness to exert extra effort at $M = 3.6588$ and $SD = .57317$, offering service as the need arises at $M = 3.6573$ and $SD = .56898$, strong belief in organizational values at $M = 3.6461$ and $SD = .59055$, and the need for supportive supervision and training at $M = 3.6397$ and $SD = .57339$, which, although still very satisfactory, was the lowest among the indicators. These results indicate that BHWs possess a strong intrinsic orientation toward service, characterized by commitment, fulfillment, and positive engagement with community health responsibilities. The comparatively lower score on supportive supervision and training highlights a structural gap, suggesting that while intrinsic motivation is robust, external organizational support remains essential for sustaining long term engagement and effectiveness, consistent with the literature emphasizing the role of supervision and capacity building in community health systems.

In terms of competency in organizing BHW orientation and building interpersonal relationships, the overall mean was $M = 3.6060$ with $SD = .37645$, interpreted as highly competent. Among the indicators, inputting data into written records had the highest mean of $M = 3.6806$ and $SD = .53025$, followed by communicating with patients face to face at $M = 3.6661$ and $SD = .57428$, working as a member of a team at $M = 3.6515$ and $SD = .60139$, developing joint work arrangements at $M = 3.6307$ and $SD = .59721$, and establishing relationships with patients at $M = 3.6279$ and $SD = .59322$. Other competencies included prioritizing work according to patient needs at $M = 3.6207$ and $SD = .60983$, undertaking health promotion and prevention activities at $M = 3.6194$ and $SD = .58274$, giving information to patients and carers at $M = 3.5935$ and $SD = .61311$, making appropriate referrals at $M = 3.5940$ and $SD = .59964$, categorizing for admission and termination at $M = 3.5889$ and $SD = .60634$, taking technical treatment procedures at $M = 3.5318$ and $SD = .67010$, and evaluating patients' psychological and social needs at $M = 3.4601$ and $SD = .73682$, which was the lowest. These findings indicate strong competency in communication, documentation, and teamwork, which are essential for primary healthcare delivery. However, the relatively lower mean for psychosocial assessment reflects a limitation in addressing mental and social health dimensions, underscoring the need for expanded training in holistic care approaches as emphasized in contemporary community health frameworks.

Competency in delivering primary healthcare services yielded an overall mean of $M = 3.6146$ and $SD = .39810$, indicating a highly competent level. Maintaining records and making reports had a mean of $M = 3.6742$ and $SD = .57027$, while collecting vital statistics recorded $M = 3.6715$ and $SD = .59294$. Assisting in health center activities had $M = 3.6570$ and $SD = .58154$, anthropometric measurement recorded $M = 3.6361$ and $SD = .61401$, assessment of vital signs had $M = 3.6231$ and $SD = .64001$, equipment sterilization had $M = 3.5799$ and $SD = .67958$, and first aid had the lowest mean of $M = 3.4583$ and $SD = .78449$. These results suggest that BHWs are highly capable in routine and preventive functions, particularly in documentation and monitoring tasks essential for health system operations. However, the lower

competency in first aid highlights a critical gap in emergency preparedness, indicating the need for enhanced training in immediate response and lifesaving interventions.

In the domain of safe motherhood and women's health, the overall mean was $M = 3.6258$ with $SD = .40564$, interpreted as highly competent. Healthy lifestyle promotion had the highest mean at $M = 3.6942$ and $SD = .55073$, followed by care during pregnancy at $M = 3.6552$ and $SD = .58358$ and family planning at $M = 3.6543$ and $SD = .59614$. Adolescent fertility recorded $M = 3.6397$ and $SD = .59515$, sexually transmitted diseases had $M = 3.5662$ and $SD = .64403$, and care during post-partum had the lowest mean at $M = 3.5454$ and $SD = .69462$. These findings demonstrate strong competency in preventive maternal health services but reveal relatively lower proficiency in post-partum care and management of sexually transmitted diseases, suggesting the need for targeted capacity building in these specialized areas to ensure comprehensive maternal healthcare delivery.

Competency in child health services showed an overall mean of $M = 3.6629$ and $SD = .40653$, also interpreted as highly competent. Sanitation and hygiene had the highest mean of $M = 3.7069$ and $SD = .53090$, followed by expanded program on immunization at $M = 3.6824$ and $SD = .53982$, growth monitoring and promotion at $M = 3.6788$ and $SD = .55102$, nutrition for children at $M = 3.6570$ and $SD = .57683$, integrated management of childhood illnesses at $M = 3.6561$ and $SD = .55132$, and control of diarrheal disease at $M = 3.5962$ and $SD = .60523$. These results indicate strong effectiveness in preventive and promotive child health programs, although the lower score in diarrheal disease management points to a need for strengthening competencies in managing common childhood illnesses.

Significant differences in attitude toward public service delivery were observed across age, educational attainment, employment status, length of service, BHW category, and municipality, while no significant differences were found based on sex and civil status. Post hoc analysis revealed that respondents aged 56–65 had a mean of $M = 3.5991$, which was significantly lower compared to those aged 26–35 with $M = 3.7281$ and those aged 46–55 with $M = 3.6918$, while other age group comparisons were not statistically significant. In terms of length of service, those with 10 years or less had $M = 3.6299$, which was significantly lower than those with 21–30 years who had $M = 3.7455$, with no other significant differences observed. These findings indicate that experience plays a critical role in shaping attitudes, with more experienced BHWs demonstrating more positive orientations toward public service. Differences across educational attainment suggest that both higher and lower educational levels may influence attitudes through role expectations and perceived alignment, while employment status findings indicate that unemployed and self-employed BHWs exhibit more positive attitudes, likely due to greater time availability. Variations across municipalities further emphasize the influence of contextual and institutional factors such as governance and resource allocation.

Similarly, competency levels showed significant differences across age, educational attainment, employment status, length of service, BHW category, and municipality, but not by sex or civil status. A significant difference was observed between younger respondents aged 26–35 and older respondents aged 56–65, suggesting that competency may be influenced by differences in adaptability and exposure to training. Respondents at the college level demonstrated higher competency compared to college graduates and those with lower educational attainment, indicating that active engagement in learning may be more influential than completed educational credentials. Unemployed and self-employed respondents exhibited higher competency levels, reinforcing the importance of time flexibility in skill development and application. Competency was highest among those with 21–30 years of service, supporting the role of accumulated experience in enhancing performance, although gains may plateau beyond this period. Volunteers demonstrated lower competency compared to registered BHWs,

highlighting the importance of formal training and system integration. Differences across municipalities further confirm that competency is shaped by contextual factors, including access to resources and local support systems.

The relationship between attitude toward public service delivery and competency was found to be strong, positive, and statistically significant, with $r = 0.758$ and $p < .001$. At the level of significance, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship was rejected. This indicates that higher levels of positive attitude are associated with higher levels of competency among BHWs. The strength of the correlation suggests that competency is not solely determined by training or experience but is also strongly influenced by intrinsic motivation and service orientation. BHWs who demonstrate greater willingness to serve, commitment to their roles, and fulfillment in helping others are more likely to exhibit higher levels of skill and effectiveness in delivering healthcare services. This finding aligns with theoretical perspectives that emphasize the role of motivation in enhancing performance and supports the view that psychological and attitudinal factors are integral to competency development in community health work.

In synthesis, the findings demonstrate that Barangay Health Workers in the First District of Capiz exhibit very satisfactory attitudes toward public service delivery and high levels of competency across multiple domains of healthcare service provision. The results reveal that intrinsic motivation, supported by experience and contextual factors, plays a critical role in shaping both attitudes and competency. While strengths are evident in preventive care, communication, and routine service delivery, gaps remain in specialized areas such as psychosocial assessment, first aid, post-partum care, and disease management, indicating the need for targeted training interventions. Significant variations across profile variables highlight the influence of experiential, educational, and institutional factors, while the strong positive relationship between attitude and competency underscores the importance of integrating motivational and skill based approaches in capacity building programs. These findings contribute to the understanding of community health workforce development and provide a basis for designing context responsive interventions aimed at enhancing both the motivation and capability of Barangay Health Workers, thereby strengthening public health service delivery systems.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study demonstrate that Barangay Health Workers in the First District of Capiz exhibit very satisfactory attitudes toward public service delivery alongside high levels of competency across essential healthcare domains. These results affirm that BHWs possess both the motivational orientation and the practical capabilities necessary to effectively deliver community-based health services. The analysis further revealed that variations in both attitude and competency are significantly influenced by factors such as age, educational attainment, employment status, length of service, BHW category, and municipality, suggesting that these characteristics shape the degree to which BHWs engage with and perform their roles. In contrast, no significant differences were observed when respondents were grouped according to sex and civil status, indicating that these variables do not substantially affect either their disposition toward public service or their level of competence. Moreover, the study established a strong positive and statistically significant relationship between attitudes toward public service delivery and competency, highlighting that BHWs who demonstrate more positive attitudes are more likely to exhibit higher levels of competence. This relationship underscores the interconnected nature of affective and skill-based dimensions in determining the effectiveness of healthcare service delivery at the community level.

Building on these findings, it becomes evident that enhancing both the attitudes and competencies of BHWs is essential for sustaining and improving the quality of public health services. Strengthening capacity building programs is therefore necessary, particularly in identified areas that require further development such as psychosocial assessment and first aid, to ensure that BHWs are adequately equipped to respond to diverse community health needs. In addition, the provision of comprehensive support systems by local government units and health authorities is crucial in maintaining positive attitudes toward public service. Such support may include recognition mechanisms, appropriate incentives, and continuous supervision, all of which contribute to reinforcing motivation and commitment among BHWs. Furthermore, promoting access to continuing education and certification opportunities can significantly enhance professional growth and competency development, thereby enabling BHWs to adapt to evolving healthcare demands. The presence of variations across municipalities and demographic groups also indicates the need for targeted and context specific interventions that address localized challenges and disparities in performance.

In light of these insights, the study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on community health workforce development by emphasizing the dual importance of attitudinal and competency based factors in achieving effective service delivery. The findings provide a basis for policy formulation and program enhancement aimed at optimizing the performance of BHWs within the local healthcare system. At the same time, the results open avenues for further investigation into other potential determinants of BHW performance, encouraging future researchers to explore additional variables and to validate the present findings across different settings. Overall, the study reinforces the critical role of Barangay Health Workers as front line providers of healthcare and highlights the need for sustained institutional support, continuous professional development, and evidence based interventions to ensure the delivery of responsive and high quality public health services.

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